

AI in Biostatistics: A project-based approach

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Abstract

The term “AI” was used loosely to describe computer bots in the past. Now, computers can perform complex tasks, and we must find ways to make a positive impact of using Artificial Intelligence in education. Through a project-based approach, students experience real-world applications of data analysis in Biology using technologies: AI, The R Program, and Adobe Portfolio. Students are guided to use free AI tools (i.e. ChatGPT) to generate biological research questions, simulate random data, and analyze the data using techniques and methods taught in class. With the help of AI tools, students learn to ask ChatGPT how to code their analysis using the (free) R Program and present their results through projects by creating a website using Adobe Portfolio. With measurable learning outcomes for the projects at the end of the semester and opportunities for formative feedback as “check points” throughout each project, students gain a better understanding of the process. This paper will discuss the project-based approach with student examples along with the results of a survey designed to gather student feedback to make enhancements in future semesters.

Key Words: AI, Adobe Portfolio, Statistical Education

1. Introduction to the Biostatistics Course

At the University of Texas at San Antonio (UTSA), the Biostatistics course is an introductory statistics course (lower level) specifically for Biology majors called Probability and Statistics for the Biosciences. It is a three-hour credit course.

1.1 Students in the Course

The typical student who takes Probability and Statistics for the Biosciences are undergraduate students in their sophomore or junior year. Algebra for the Biosciences and Calculus for the Biosciences are pre-requisites for the course. There are, on average, 300 students each long semester who take this course across two sections (one asynchronous online and one traditional face-to-face section).

1.1.1 Probability and Statistics for the Biosciences course

The probability and statistics for biosciences course is a 16-week semester long course in both Spring and Fall, and 10-week long course in summer. The course is broken down into three units throughout the semester:

Unit 1: Descriptive Statistics

- Introduction to Statistics
- Numerical Summaries
- Graphical Representations
- Probability
- Probability Distributions

Unit 2: One-sample and Two-Sample Inference

- One-sample Confidence Intervals and Hypothesis Tests

- Two-Sample Confidence Intervals and Hypothesis Test for Independent Samples
- Matched Pairs Test

Unit 3: Additional Inference

- Chi-Square Tests
- One-way and Two-way Analysis of Variance
- Simple Linear Regression
- Multiple Regression

2. The Project-based Approach

The projects being described are suitable for various modalities. Specifically for this paper, the projects were designed and offered to students in one section of Probability and Statistics for the Biosciences in the asynchronous online modality. Three projects were offered:

- Project 1: My R Journey
- Project 2: Descriptive Statistics
- Project 3: Inferential Statistics

The main goal of the series of projects was to encourage the use of technologies to simulate, analyze, and display the results of a data analysis related to a biological research question. Technologies utilized throughout these projects were:

- AI through ChatGPT. Students were required to use the free version of ChatGPT (or a paid subscription if they chose to do so).
- R Studio. A free, open-source integrated development environment for the R programming language.
- Adobe Portfolio. A web-based tool to build and launch personalized portfolio websites. Free for students at UTSA through a University Adobe license.

Keeping these projects at zero extra cost for students to complete. Students were encouraged to be creative with their projects by designing and personalizing their portfolio pages to make them unique. Utilize research questions that were of interest to them and make their portfolio eye catching and interesting to the viewer.

2.1 Project 1

Project 1 was titled “My R Journey”. Students in this course are not required to have any previous R (or R Studio) experience. It is not a coding class. Focus remains on computations and formulas to analyze data. However, RStudio is utilized in conjunction with class lecture to perform analyses on larger datasets and more in depth topics such as Two-way Analysis of Variance and Multiple Regression towards the end of the semester. The project objectives:

- Design a personal portfolio project that includes a home page with text and images
- Create pages within your portfolio with appropriate navigation
- Use appropriate settings and content creation tools within Adobe Portfolio
- Use ChatGPT to answer a series of questions
- Use ChatGPT to provide research questions in the field of Biology

Project 1 was designed to familiarize students with using Adobe Portfolio and ChatGPT. Students were able to follow video tutorials to set up their personal (free) webpage and create navigation buttons as a place to house all three projects throughout the semester. The home page, being Project 1, required two visual aids: a photo that describes them and a photo that describes their interest in the field of Biology. The goal of this part of the project was to personalize their portfolio and make it unique to them. All photos in their projects needed to be either original photos or open-sourced. Then, weaving in an introduction to ChatGPT and utilizing OpenAI to help in writing code in RStudio and types of questions that can be asked. Students were guided to ask ChatGPT a series of

questions and any additional questions they felt like asking about how it would be useful throughout these projects. The last part was to explain their interests in Biology to ChatGPT and ask ChatGPT to generate some research questions in the field of Biology.

2.2 Project 2

Project 2 was titled “Descriptive Statistics” assigned before midterm. Navigating to the second page of their Adobe portfolio, students would continue to build on Project 1. The project objectives:

- Use ChatGPT to generate random data
- Use ChatGPT to assist in R code
- Summarize data using numerical summaries
- Display data with appropriate graphical displays
- Upload to your Adobe Portfolio

Using one of the ChatGPT generated research questions from Project 1, students asked Chat GPT to provide a simulated dataset based on that research question for a sample size of 50 that included three qualitative variables and three quantitative variables. From this simulated dataset, students then had to choose an appropriate graphical display for a minimum of one qualitative variable and one quantitative variable from their study along with appropriate numerical summaries to include mean, median, min, max, variance, range and standard deviation to summarize their quantitative variables. Students were directed to ask ChatGPT a series of questions specific to the variables in their analysis in order to generate code for RStudio. Then continuously asking follow up questions to ChatGPT in order to provide the best graphical displays and correct numerical summaries for their analysis. Students confirmed these results were correct using methods taught in class through hand calculations. Students were reminded that ChatGPT is not 100% accurate. Meaning they should not reply completely on what ChatGPT provides them, so they need to verify the analysis by using methods learned in class. Once all analyses were performed, students input their findings into page 2 of their Adobe Portfolio. The Adobe Portfolio included the research question of interest, all questions asked to ChatGPT during their analysis, an excerpt of their simulated dataset, numerical summaries for their quantitative variables, a minimum of two graphical displays, and a written portion containing 2-3 sentences describing the findings for their research questions based on the analyses provided in the portfolio. The RStudio code was added at the bottom of the portfolio in a textbox section that would be copied and pasted during grading to check for accuracy and correctness.

2.3 Project 3

Project 3 was titled “Inferential Statistics” assigned after midterm. Navigating to the third page of their portfolio, students once again continued to build on the previous projects. The project objectives:

- Use ChatGPT to research your topic of interest
- Use ChatGPT to assist in R code
- Summarize data using descriptive statistics and graphical displays
- Analyze data using a one-sample test
- Analyze data using a one-sample confidence interval
- Upload to your Adobe Portfolio

Choosing one of their research questions from project 1, students were guided to research their topic using ChatGPT. Asking a series of questions to ChatGPT to simulate a dataset for their research question with a sample size of 25 and one quantitative variable. Based on this simulated dataset, students were asked to summarize their data using appropriate descriptive statistics and graphical displays. They asked ChatGPT what an appropriate hypothesized value would be to run a one sample hypothesis test on their data. Using this hypothesized value, students asked ChatGPT to produce the RStudio code to run a one sample t-test for a population mean along with the associated

confidence interval on their data. They were instructed to continue asking questions to ChatGPT to tweak the R Studio code in order to generate correct output and display numerical summaries and graphical displays that were of use in their analysis. Once students verified their results were correct using hand calculations and formulas shown in class, they were directed to display their analysis in their Adobe Portfolio. The Adobe Portfolio included their research question, the simulated dataset, numerical summaries, graphical displays, RStudio output for the hypothesis test and confidence interval, along with 3-4 written sentences concluding their analysis and showing the testing procedure on their data. The R Studio code was added at the bottom of the portfolio in a textbook section that would be copied and pasted during grading to check for accuracy and correctness.

3. Student Portfolio Examples

3.1 Project 1 Student Example

My R Journey

Here is a picture that describes me (left) and a picture that is meaningful to me in my field of biology (right).

Research Questions

- What are the effects of prenatal stress on the development of the fetal brain?
- How do neuropeptides like oxytocin influence social bonding and behaviors in mammals?
- How does the functional connectivity of brain networks differ among individuals who excel in specific domains, such as mathematics or art, compared to those who do not?

What is R?

R is a powerful programming language specifically designed for statistical computing and data visualization. It is widely used in biostatistics for analyzing and interpreting complex data sets, especially in fields like genomics, epidemiology, and clinical trials.

How R is used in Biostatistics:

Data Cleaning and Preparation: R has functions to clean and preprocess raw data, handling missing values, filtering, or transforming variables.

Statistical Tests: R provides built-in functions for various statistical tests like t-tests, chi-squared tests, ANOVA, etc.

Regression Models: Biostatistics frequently involves linear and logistic regression to predict outcomes or model relationships between variables, which R excels at.

Survival Analysis: R is widely used for survival analysis, which is key in medical research (e.g., Kaplan-Meier estimators).

Visualization: R's packages, like ggplot2, help create meaningful plots (histograms, scatter plots, etc.) to better interpret and present data.

Can you help write R code?

I can help you write R code! If you have a specific dataset or task in mind, I can guide you step by step or create a basic template to get you started. Let me know what you're aiming to do!

I have never used R before, will it be difficult to learn?

Since you've never used R before, it might seem unfamiliar at first, but many people find R to be beginner-friendly, especially with the right guidance and practice.

3.2 Project 2 Student Example

Descriptive Statistics

Research Question:

In what ways is climate change disrupting animal behavior and habitats?

Questions for ChatGPT:

- In what ways is climate change disrupting animal behavior and habitats?
- Provide me with the following for my research question: A sample size of 50; 3 numerical variables; 3 categorical variables
- Generate the RStudio code to enter the simulated data
- Output the first 6 observations using the head () command in RStudio.
- Provide descriptive statistics for all 3 of my numerical variables.
- Generate the RStudio code to provide Descriptive Statistics on each of these variables (include the mean, median, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum)
- Provide 2 separate graphical displays to summarize my data. One graph will be for a numerical variable, the other graph for a categorical variable.
- Generate the RStudio code for these graphs.
- Provide the code to export the graphs and save to use in my portfolio.

Simulated Data:

The 6 Observations of My Simulated Dataset are species, habitat type, behavior change, temperature increase, migration distance, and food availability.

Climate Change Disruption Data With Food Availability

	Species	Habitat_Type	Behavior_Change	Temperature_Increase	Migration_Distance	Food_Availability
1	Reptile	Forest	Yes	2.217591	114.79895	10.169475
2	Reptile	Forest	No	1.837034	138.18207	11.508108
3	Reptile	Tundra	No	2.574404	71.12214	9.001416
4	Mammal	Forest	Yes	2.496752	114.03569	10.428891
5	Reptile	Desert	Yes	2.274198	94.75605	9.350628
6	Mammal	Forest	Yes	2.119366	68.55712	10.189167

Count of Species Affected by Climate Change

Distribution of Temperature Increase in Animal Habitats

Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Mean	Median	SD	Min	Max
Temperature Increase	1.964692	1.923248	0.4607835	0.9733764	3.093666
Migration Distance	100.294956	96.833715	21.0851777	67.9692765	164.820799
Food Availability	9.925151	9.410169	1.8871844	7.3659677	14.397621

```

#Simulated Data
set.seed(123)

# Create categorical variables
species <- sample(c("Bird", "Mammal", "Reptile"), size = 50, replace = TRUE)
habitat_type <- sample(c("Forest", "Desert", "Tundra"), size = 50, replace = TRUE)
behavior_change <- sample(c("Yes", "No"), size = 50, replace = TRUE)

# Create numerical variables
temperature_increase <- rnorm(50, mean = 2, sd = 0.5) # Simulating temp increase in °C
migration_distance <- rnorm(50, mean = 100, sd = 20) # Simulating migration distance in km
food_availability <- rnorm(50, mean = 10, sd = 2) # Simulating food availability in kg

# Combine into a data frame
climate_data <- data.frame(
  Species = species,
  Habitat_Type = habitat_type,
  Behavior_Change = behavior_change,
  Temperature_Increase = temperature_increase,
  Migration_Distance = migration_distance,
  Food_Availability = food_availability
)

# Display first 6 observations
head(climate_data)

#Descriptive Statistics
# Temperature Increase
temp_mean <- mean(climate_data$Temperature_Increase)
temp_median <- median(climate_data$Temperature_Increase)
temp_sd <- sd(climate_data$Temperature_Increase)
temp_min <- min(climate_data$Temperature_Increase)
temp_max <- max(climate_data$Temperature_Increase)

# Migration Distance
mig_mean <- mean(climate_data$Migration_Distance)
mig_median <- median(climate_data$Migration_Distance)
mig_sd <- sd(climate_data$Migration_Distance)
mig_min <- min(climate_data$Migration_Distance)
mig_max <- max(climate_data$Migration_Distance)

# Food Availability
food_mean <- mean(climate_data$Food_Availability)
food_median <- median(climate_data$Food_Availability)
food_sd <- sd(climate_data$Food_Availability)
food_min <- min(climate_data$Food_Availability)
food_max <- max(climate_data$Food_Availability)

# Combine descriptive stats into a data frame
descriptive_stats <- data.frame(
  Variable = c("Temperature Increase", "Migration Distance", "Food Availability"),
  Mean = c(temp_mean, mig_mean, food_mean),
  Median = c(temp_median, mig_median, food_median),
  SD = c(temp_sd, mig_sd, food_sd),
  Min = c(temp_min, mig_min, food_min),
  Max = c(temp_max, mig_max, food_max)
)

# View the descriptive statistics table
print(descriptive_stats)

#Graphs
#Graph 1: Histogram for Temperature Increase
hist(climate_data$Temperature_Increase,
main = "Distribution of Temperature Increase in Animal Habitats",
xlab = "Temperature Increase (°C)",
col = "lightblue",
border = "black",
breaks = 10)

# Save the histogram as a PNG
png("Temperature_Increase_Histogram.png")
hist(climate_data$Temperature_Increase,
main = "Distribution of Temperature Increase in Animal Habitats",
xlab = "Temperature Increase (°C)",
col = "lightblue",
border = "black",
breaks = 10)
dev.off()

#Graph 2: Bar Plot for Species
species_count <- table(climate_data$Species)
barplot_height <- barplot(species_count,
main = "Count of Species Affected by Climate Change",
xlab = "Species",
ylab = "Count",
col = c("lightgreen", "lightcoral", "lightblue"),
border = "black")

```

The data reveals that temperature increases in animal habitats due to climate change generally fall within the range of approximately 1 to 3°C, with a slight concentration around 2°C. Additionally, the bar plot shows that the most represented species in this sample are reptiles, followed by mammals, indicating that reptiles may be particularly affected in the studied regions. These results suggest that climate change is impacting different species and environments in diverse ways.

3.3 Project 3 Student Example

Inferential Statistics

How Do Some Animals Regenerate Lost Body Parts

1. Generate new research questions related to animal regeneration for a data analysis project.
2. Simulate data for a sample size of 25 with one numerical variable representing regeneration time in days.
3. Provide RStudio code to generate the simulated data for this variable.
4. How do I format the simulated dataset into a comma-separated list for my portfolio?
5. Provide RStudio code to calculate descriptive statistics for the simulated data, including count, mean, median, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum.
6. What additional descriptive statistics can I include for my dataset?
7. Generate RStudio code to create a histogram for the simulated data with meaningful titles and labels.
8. Generate RStudio code to create a boxplot for the simulated data with meaningful titles and labels.
9. How can I adjust the appearance of the graphs, such as changing colors or adding labels?
10. What is a reasonable hypothesized population mean for regeneration time in days?
11. Provide RStudio code to run a one-sample t-test for the mean regeneration time, assuming a 5% significance level and a two-tailed alternative hypothesis.
12. Provide RStudio code to calculate the 95% confidence interval for the mean regeneration time.
13. How do I interpret the results of the t-test for my portfolio?
14. How do I organize my Adobe Portfolio for this project?
15. What elements should I include in the Inferential Statistics page of my portfolio?
16. How should I format and label graphs and tables in my portfolio?

#Simulated Data

Regeneration Time (days):

12.2, 13.8, 22.8, 15.4, 15.6, 23.6, 17.3, 8.7, 11.6, 12.8, 21.1, 16.8, 17.0, 15.6, 12.2, 23.9, 17.5, 5.2, 18.5, 12.6, 9.7, 13.9, 9.9, 11.4, 11.9

#Graph

Histogram of Regeneration Time

Boxplot of Regeneration Time

Summary Statistics for Days to Regeneration

```
> print(summary_table)
```

	Sample_Size	Mean	Median	Minimum	Maximum	Standard_Deviation
1	25	14.836	13.9	5.2	23.9	4.722453

The hypothesized population mean for regeneration time in days can be based on prior research or biological context. Assuming a typical regeneration time of 15 days for the species or scenario in question, we can use this as the hypothesized mean ($\mu_0 = 15$). This value represents the null hypothesis (H_0) for the one-sample t-test, where we test whether the mean regeneration time of the sample differs significantly from 15 days.

#Hypothesis Test

Based on the provided t-test results, here is the hypothesis testing procedure :

1. Hypotheses:

- Null Hypothesis (H_0): The mean regeneration time is 15 days ($\mu = 15$).
- Alternative Hypothesis (H_a): The mean regeneration time is not 15 days ($\mu \neq 15$).

2. Test Statistic

The calculated test statistic is:

$$t = -0.16938$$

Degrees of freedom (df): 24

3. P-value

The p-value for the test is:

$$p = 0.8669$$

- Since ($p > 0.05$), we fail to reject the null hypothesis at a 5% significance level.

4. Conclusion

Based on the p-value ($p = 0.8669$), there is insufficient evidence to conclude that the mean regeneration time differs significantly from 15 days.

- The 95% confidence interval for the mean is [12.89041, 16.78959], which includes the hypothesized value of 15 days.
- Final Interpretation: The sample mean regeneration time of 14.84 days does not significantly differ from the hypothesized population mean of 15 days.

One Sample t-test

```
data: regeneration_time
t = -0.16938, df = 24, p-value = 0.8669
alternative hypothesis: true mean is not equal to 15
95 percent confidence interval:
 12.89041 16.78959
sample estimates:
mean of x
 14.84
```

#Confidence Interval

The 95% confidence interval for the mean regeneration time is [12.89, 16.79] days. This means that we are 95% confident that the true population mean regeneration time lies between 12.89 days and 16.79 days. Since the hypothesized mean of 15 days falls within this interval, there is insufficient evidence to suggest that the mean regeneration time differs significantly from 15 days.

```

# Simulated Data
set.seed(123) # for reproducibility
regeneration_time <- round(rnorm(25, mean = 15, sd = 5), 1) # mean = 15 days, sd = 5 days
regeneration_time

# Descriptive Statistics
summary_stats <- summary(regeneration_time)
sd_value <- sd(regeneration_time)
data_summary <- cbind(summary_stats, sd_value)
data_summary

# Graphs
## Histogram
hist(regeneration_time,
     main = "Histogram of Regeneration Time",
     xlab = "Time (days)",
     ylab = "Frequency",
     col = "lightblue",
     border = "black")

## Boxplot
boxplot(regeneration_time,
       main = "Boxplot of Regeneration Time",
       ylab = "Time (days)",
       col = "lightgreen")

# Hypothesis Testing
## One-Sample T-Test
t_test <- t.test(regeneration_time, mu = 15, conf.level = 0.95)
t_test

```

4. Student Survey Results

A pre project survey was given to all students in the course. A post project survey was given to students who completed all three projects. Results were collected and analyzed from students who completed both the pre and post project survey (n = 74 over Fall 2024 and Spring 2025).

4.1 Survey Results

Questions 1 – 3: Familiarity with Various Technologies

Scale:

1 - not familiar with and have never used it

5 - very familiar and have used it often

Technology	Pre-project Average	Post-project Average
ChatGPT	3.27	4.14
R Statistical Program	1.55	3.26
Adobe Portfolio	2.19	3.62

Table 1. Familiarity with Various Technologies

Questions 4 – 6: Attitude Towards Various Technologies

Figure 1. Student Attitude Towards ChatGPT

Figure 2. Student Attitude Towards Adobe Portfolio

Figure 3. Student Attitude Towards RStudio

Questions 7 – 9: Likeliness to use Various Technologies after this course (from post-project survey)

Technology	More Likely	Less Likely
ChatGPT	91.9%	8.1%
R Statistical Program	73.0%	27.0%
Adobe Portfolio	82.4%	17.6%

Table2. Likeliness to use Various Technologies

4.2 Student Comments

In addition to the survey questions, students were given an optional free response question to elaborate.

“Using the technologies described during these set of projects was a good experience; it allowed me to create an outline and ask various types of questions. Of course, this kind of technology is not always accurate so there are some specific questions that you may have to ask. But it was interesting to see how all these technologies could help gather the information like graphs and tables that I needed for these projects.” ~Student 1

“I have learned a lot about using ChatGPT to generate code and simulate data. RStudio has proven very useful for complicated statistical calculations and as someone who is involved in research, I foresee myself using this software again for analysis and visualization. I also like the graphing function in R studio. I already use Adobe Portfolio for my study abroad blog so I think I will continue to use it more to document things.” ~Student 2

4.3 Next Steps

After piloting these projects for two long semesters, there are updates that can be made based on student feedback and results. Project wording will need to be clarified and provide student examples from previous semesters. This will give students a guide on how the project should look but still encouraged to make it their own. More detailed rubrics will be developed to guide students through exact expectations of each project and make it easier and less time consuming to grade. There is a lot of opportunity to add additional projects into the portfolio to include two sample inferencing, ANOVA, and/or Regression.

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